

Mapping Research Topics on Price Earning Ratio (PER) on Islamic and Conventional Banking: VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Literature Review

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Abstract

This study aims to determine the research mapping regarding the Price Earning Ratio (PER) ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking using a mix-method approach, namely the VOSviewer bibliometric study and literature review. Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications around the PER ratio; (2) mapping the results of the VOSviewer bibliometric visualization around the PER ratio based on the number of clusters and their items; and (3) mapping research topics around the PER ratio using a literature review study. The results showed that: (1) based on the distribution of journal publications, there were 571 journal publications regarding the PER ratio; (2) based on the mapping of the VOSviewer bibliometric study, the network visualization results around the PER ratio are divided into 4 clusters and 178 topic items; (3) based on the mapping of literature review studies, there are 31 topics around the influence of the PER ratio and 49 topics about the determinants of the PER ratio. The implications and contributions of this research are to map research topics around PER ratios in Islamic and Conventional Banking which are often or rarely researched by researchers so that they can be a reference for subsequent researchers.

Keywords: Price Earning Ratio (PER), Bibliometrics, VOSviewer, Literature Review, Islamic and Conventional Banking

Introduction

In the banking context, Price Earning Ratio (PER) It is also often used to assess bank financial performance. However, because banks have different business characteristics from other companies, PER is not always the main benchmark in assessing bank performance. Bank financial performance is influenced by various factors, such as risk policies taken by the bank, market performance, economic conditions, and so on. Therefore, several research companies and financial institutions still use PER as an indicator of bank financial performance. In this case, PER is used as a financial performance analysis tool which can provide a reasonable picture of bank share prices compared to the net profit generated by the bank.

Apart from that, PER is also used as a tool to compare the financial performance of one bank with another. Investors and financial analysts can compare the PER of several banks in the same industry to see how one bank's financial performance compares to others. However, it should be remembered that the use of PER as a tool for analyzing banking financial performance must be done carefully. PER only provides an overview of the bank's financial performance at a certain time and cannot guarantee the bank's financial performance in the future. Therefore, investors and financial analysts need to use various other financial performance indicators in assessing bank financial performance, such as Return on Equity (ROE), Return on Assets (ROA), Net Interest Margin (NIM), and so on.

There are several studies regarding the use of PER in assessing banking financial performance. Some of this research includes: first, research shows that PER can be used as a financial performance indicator that can predict bank stock performance in the future. This research shows that banks with lower PER tend to have better stock performance in the future. Second, research shows that PER has a positive relationship with bank financial performance. The results of this research show that banks with higher PER tend to have higher ROA and ROE. Third, research shows that PER can be used as an effective analysis tool for bank financial performance in predicting credit risk. The results of this research show that banks with lower PER tend to have lower credit risk. Fourth, research shows different results that PER does not have a significant relationship with bank financial performance. Overall, the use of PER in assessing banking financial performance is still an active and growing research topic. Some studies show that PER can be used as an effective financial performance indicator, while other studies show different results. Therefore, the use of PER in assessing banking financial performance must be done carefully and must be balanced with the use of other financial performance indicators.

The aim of this research is to map research topics around PER in Sharia and Conventional Banking using: (1) the VOSviewer bibliometric method to analyze and study maps of literature development in publications in a scientific field by creating a metadata network map; and (2) literature study review to analyze, identify and review articles from the accredited national journal Sinta. The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains all research topics surrounding PER. This can be a reference for other researchers who wish to research PER. The implication and contribution of this research is to map research topics around the PER ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking which are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that they can become a reference for subsequent researchers.

Literature Review

Price Earning Ratio (PER) is the ratio between a company's share price and its earnings per share. PER is used to measure how much investors must pay for each dollar of profit generated by a company. In the banking context, PER is an important measure for assessing bank financial performance. A higher PER indicates that investors are more optimistic about the company's prospects, while a lower PER may indicate uncertainty or concern about the company's future performance. However, when comparing PER between banks, there are special factors that need to be considered, such as interest rates, credit risk, and competition in the market. Therefore, PER should be analyzed along with other financial metrics to get a more complete picture of a company's performance.

Bibliometric studies are a research method used to analyze and measure scientific publications in a particular field, using quantitative data. In bibliometric studies, the data analyzed includes information about the number of publications, authors, subjects, publication sources, citations, and impact factor. The goal of bibliometric studies is to provide an overview of trends and patterns in scientific publications, as well as measure the impact of these publications on the academic community and industry. Bibliometric studies can be used to identify emerging research areas, measure research performance, and compare performance between researchers, institutions, or countries. Bibliometric studies are usually carried out using bibliometric software, such as Web of Science, Scopus, or Google Scholar. Bibliometric methods can also be

used to conduct qualitative analysis, such as content analysis or other qualitative analysis, to understand the issues expressed in certain scientific publications.

VOSviewer is open source software used in bibliometric studies to visualize and analyze the network of links between documents or scientific publications. VOSviewer can be used to analyze bibliometric data collected from various sources, such as Scopus, Web of Science, or Google Scholar. VOSviewer can be used to perform quantitative and qualitative analysis, such as cluster identification, citation analysis, and topic mapping. In cluster analysis, VOSviewer can group scientific publications into similar groups based on their association with a particular topic. Citation analysis can be used to identify the most cited scientific publications in a research field. Topic mapping can be used to identify the most widely discussed research topics in a field. One of the advantages of VOSviewer is its ability to produce attractive and easy-to-understand visualizations, such as heatmaps, network graphs and topic trees. This visualization can help researchers understand patterns and trends in bibliometric data more easily and quickly. VOSviewer can be used by researchers, academics, and practitioners in various research fields, including social science, information science, health, and information technology.

Literature review study is a research method used to collect, evaluate, and analyze literature or scientific publications related to a particular research topic. The purpose of a literature review study is to provide a comprehensive understanding of the research that has been conducted in a particular field and to identify gaps in existing research. Literature review studies can be carried out using various sources of information, such as academic journals, books and other documents. Researchers can use certain criteria to select literature that is relevant to their research topic, such as publication date, research methods, or type of publication. After relevant literature has been collected, researchers conduct analysis of the collected data to identify patterns and trends in existing research. Researchers can then evaluate the quality of existing research and identify gaps in research that need further research. Literature review studies are very useful in research because they can help researchers understand the research topic better and develop more focused research questions. Literature review studies can also help researchers identify theories and methods that suit their research topic.

Methodology

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in literature review studies. The object of the research is Price Earning Ratio (PER). The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is research journal articles on PER in Sharia and Conventional Banking.

The source of data collection comes from searches of accredited national journals, Sinta via the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba) and Perish/Harzing software. Data analysis tools use Microsoft Excel, Mendeley Desktop, and VOSviewer software. Data collection techniques include: (1) opening the Perish/Harzing software, then searching for journals based on the title words category with the key words "Price Earning Ratio" and "PER" within the entire year period; (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for

which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications around PER using Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop based on year of publication; (2) mapping bibliometric network visualization results and journal publication trends about PER using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) mapping research topics around PER using a literature review study.

Results and Discussion

Mapping the Distribution of Scientific Publications around Price Earning Ratio (PER) in Sharia and Conventional Banking

There are 571 Sinta accredited national journal based on the results of data collection using Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop originating from the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba) and Perish/Harzing software during the period 2001 to 2023. The results are as follows:

Table 1. Journal publication data regarding PER by year

Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications
2001	1	2011	8	2018	44
2003	1	2012	13	2019	73
2004	1	2013	24	2020	56
2005	1	2014	43	2021	84
2008	3	2015	36	2022	76
2009	1	2016	51	2023	7
2010	7	2017	41		

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

VOSviewer Bibliometric Study Mapping About Price Earning Ratio (PER) in Sharia and Conventional Banking

Article search results in Perish/Harzing software are exported in RIS (Research Information Systems) format, then input and analyzed using VOSviewer software. The results are as follows:

- Cluster 3 consists of 42 topic items, namely: fundamental analysis, approach, capital market, condition, decision, development, dividend payout ratio, dpr, dps, financial performance/ratio, form, fund, fundamental analysis/variable, future, index, Indonesian stock exchange, intrinsic value, investment, investment decision, investor, Jakarta Islamic Index, Jii, investment decision, market price, model, performance, purposive sampling technique, quantitative approach, researcher, risk, stock, share, stock market/price, tbk, undervalued condition.
- Cluster 4 consists of 3 topic items, namely: book value, pbv, price book value.

Mapping Literature Review Study regarding the Influence of Price Earning Ratio (PER) on Sharia and Conventional Banking

Literature review study in previous research journals, researchers found 31 influences of PER on Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely:

(1) Stock beta. Stock beta measures a stock's volatility relative to market movements. The higher a stock's beta, the greater the risk associated with that stock. PER can affect stock beta, because when PER increases, the stock price will rise and can increase its volatility. Therefore, the relationship between PER and stock beta needs to be analyzed in more depth to determine the influence of PER on stock beta in the banking sector.

(2) Cumulative Abnormal Return. Cumulative abnormal return (CAR) measures the unexpected increase or decrease in stock prices and is not influenced by overall market movements. PER can affect CAR, because when PER increases, investors can have higher expectations about the company's performance and can buy those shares, which can increase the share price and its CAR. However, the relationship between PER and CAR needs to be analyzed in more depth to determine the influence of PER on CAR in the banking sector.

(3) Debt to Equity Ratio/DER. Debt to Equity Ratio (DER) measures the ratio between a company's debt and equity. The higher the DER, the greater the company's financial risk, because the company has to pay interest on its debt. PER can affect DER, because when PER increases, a company can experience increased demand for its shares and can issue new shares to finance company growth rather than taking out loans. Therefore, the relationship between PER and DER needs to be analyzed in more depth to determine the influence of PER on DER in the banking sector.

(4) Share price. Banking share prices are influenced by many factors, including PER. When PER increases, share prices also tend to increase because investors have higher expectations about the company's performance. However, PER is not always the main factor in determining share prices, because there are other factors that can influence share prices, such as market conditions, company performance, and industry news.

(5) Intrinsic share prices. The intrinsic price of shares is the fair value of shares calculated based on fundamental company factors such as earnings, cash flow and growth. PER can influence the intrinsic price of shares, because the higher the PER, the more expensive the company's shares are valued compared to the net profit per share generated. However, the fair value of shares is also influenced by other factors such as company growth prospects, business risks, and macroeconomic factors, so PER is not the only factor that influences the intrinsic price of shares.

(6) Investment decisions. Investment decisions in banking are influenced by many factors, including PER. Investors can use PER to compare share prices between similar companies in the banking sector and determine which ones are valued lower or higher compared to the industry average. However, investment decisions are not only based on PER, but must also consider other factors such as financial performance, business strategy, market risk, and other factors.

(7) Dividend policy. Banking dividend policies are usually based on the profits generated by the company and the need to maintain liquidity. PER can influence dividend policy, because the higher the PER, the higher investors' expectations for future profit growth and dividend growth. However, dividend policy is also influenced by other factors such as the need to strengthen capital, tax policy and the availability of cash funds.

(8) Corporate social performance. PER does not directly affect corporate social performance, because corporate social performance is not directly related to the company's financial performance. However, a high PER value can indicate that the company is developing well and performing well financially. This can enable companies to more easily implement social performance programs that can improve the company's image in the eyes of the public.

(9) Financial performance. PER can influence banking financial performance, because the higher the PER, the higher investors' expectations of profit growth and income growth in the future. This can encourage banks to expand their business and improve the company's financial performance. However, a PER that is too high can also indicate that the company's shares are valued more expensively compared to its fundamental value, and can cause a decline in share prices if investor expectations are not met.

(10) Portfolio performance. PER can affect the portfolio performance of investors who invest in banking shares, because shares with a high PER tend to be considered more expensive and have higher risks than shares with a low PER. However, portfolio performance is also influenced by other factors such as portfolio diversification, market risk, and overall company performance.

(11) Company profits. PER can affect company profits, because the higher the PER, the higher investors' expectations of profit growth and revenue growth in the future. This can encourage companies to expand their business and increase company revenue and profits. However, a PER that is too high can also indicate that the company's shares are valued more expensively compared to its fundamental value, and can cause a decline in share prices if investor expectations are not met.

(12) Working capital. PER does not directly affect banking working capital, because working capital is related to the company's liquidity and operational efficiency. However, a high PER can strengthen the banking position in the market and increase the company's ability to obtain financial resources from the capital market. This can help companies to strengthen working capital and improve operational efficiency.

(13) Net Asset Value/NAV. NAV is the total value of a company's assets after deducting the value of its liabilities. PER does not directly affect NAV, because NAV is influenced by the value of the company's assets and liabilities. However, PER can affect the company's share price and the market value of the company, which can then affect NAV.

(14) Company value. Company value can be influenced by PER because PER reflects investors' expectations of the company's future performance. The higher the PER, the higher investors' expectations of the company's future performance, which can increase the company's value. However, a PER that is

too high can also indicate that the company's shares are valued more expensively compared to its fundamental value, and can cause a decline in share prices which can reduce the value of the company.

(15) Income smoothing. Income smoothing is the practice of reducing profit fluctuations in a certain period to show the stability of company performance. PER can influence the practice of income smoothing, because the higher the PER, the greater the pressure to show stable performance to meet investor expectations. However, the practice of income smoothing can also have negative consequences and may raise questions about the reliability of a company's financial reporting.

(16) Stock prospects. PER can influence the prospects of a company's shares, because PER reflects investors' expectations of the company's future performance. The higher the PER, the greater investors' expectations of the company's future performance, and the higher the prospects for the company's shares. However, the company's success in meeting these expectations can be influenced by other factors such as financial performance, competition and market situation.

(17) Stock income. PER can affect investors' share income, because high share prices will increase investors' share income. However, an investor's stock income can also be influenced by other factors such as dividends and portfolio performance.

(18) Revenue growth. PER can influence revenue growth by indicating the level of investor confidence in the bank's business prospects. If the PER is high, then investors consider the bank to have good prospects, which can increase investor confidence and interest in buying shares in the bank. This in turn can increase demand for the bank's shares and increase the share price.

(19) Dividend distribution. PER can also influence a bank's dividend policy. Banks that have a high PER usually have a lower dividend policy, because they tend to retain their profits for future business growth and expansion. However, if the PER is low, then the bank tends to have a higher dividend policy to attract investor interest.

(20) Market performance. PER can also influence overall market performance, because many investors consider PER as an indicator of market confidence in bank performance. If the PER is high, then the market tends to be positive towards the bank and predicts strong growth in the future, which can increase share prices and investor interest in buying bank shares.

(21) Price Book Value/PBV. PER can also affect PBV, which indicates how much the company's market value is compared to its book value. If PER is high, then PBV tends to be high because investors pay a higher price for each unit of profit generated by the bank.

(22) Stock portfolio return. PER can also influence stock portfolio returns because many investors consider PER as a factor in choosing shares to buy. If the PER is high, then the bank's shares tend to attract investor interest, which can increase demand for the shares and increase the share price. This in turn can increase stock portfolio returns.

(23) Return On Assets/ROA. PER can influence ROA by indicating how high investors' expected profits are. If the PER is high, then investors tend to expect greater profits and if the bank cannot meet these expectations, then the ROA tends to be lower.

(24) Return On Equity/ROE. The effect of PER on ROE can vary depending on the bank's capital structure. If the bank has a good and efficient capital structure, a high PER can increase ROE because the bank can utilize

funds collected from investors to increase profits and ROE. However, if the bank's capital structure is poor, then a high PER can worsen ROE because the bank cannot generate optimal profits from invested capital.

(25) Stock market returns. PER can influence stock market returns by influencing investors' interest in buying or selling bank shares. If the PER is high, investors tend to think that the bank has bright business prospects and generates large profits, which can increase investors' interest in buying shares in the bank and ultimately increase stock market returns.

(26) Systematic risk. Systematic risk is risk that is related to the market as a whole and cannot be avoided. PER can influence systematic risk by influencing overall market performance. If the PER is high and the market is positive towards the bank, then systematic risk tends to be low because the overall market performance is good.

(27) Capital structure. Capital structure is how banks finance their operations and investments through debt and equity. PER can influence capital structure by influencing the bank's cost of capital. If PER is high, then banks can borrow at lower costs because of the high level of investor confidence, which can increase bank debt and ultimately affect the bank's capital structure. However, keep in mind that a capital structure that relies too much on debt can also increase the bank's financial risk.

(28) Underpricing of initial shares. PER can influence the underpricing of initial shares in banking. If a bank's PER is low, investors may view the company's valuation as low, making it difficult for the bank to sell initial shares at a high price.

(29) Stock rate of return. The PER level can affect the level of stock returns or return on investment. If the PER is high, it means investors have to pay a higher price to buy the shares, which in turn can reduce the rate of return on investment. Conversely, if the PER is low, investors can buy shares at a lower price, which can increase the rate of return on investment.

(30) Stock valuation. PER can influence share valuation in banking. If the PER is high, it means investors have to pay a higher price to buy the stock, which can make the stock valuation higher. However, if PER is low, stock valuation will tend to be lower.

(31) Stock trading volume. PER can influence the volume of stock trading in banking. If the PER is high, it means the stock is considered expensive and will not attract the interest of many investors, resulting in low trading volume. Conversely, if the PER is low, investors might buy the shares because they are considered undervalued, thereby increasing trading volume.

Mapping Literature Review Studies regarding the Determinant Variables of Price Earning Ratio (PER) in Sharia and Conventional Banking

Literature review study in previous research journals, researchers found 49 determinant variables of PER in Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely:

(1) Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR. CAR is a ratio that measures a bank's ability to fulfill its financial obligations. Banks that have a high CAR are considered to have a better ability to bear risks and maintain financial stability. In this case, banks that have a high CAR will tend to have a higher PER because they are considered safer and valued more highly by investors.

(2) Corporate Social Responsibility/CSR. Increasing company performance in terms of social responsibility can improve investors' and society's perception of the company. Companies that demonstrate good CSR performance are considered more socially responsible and are valued more

highly by society and investors. This can affect the company's PER, because investors will tend to give higher value to companies that are considered to have good social responsibility.

(3) Current Ratio. Current Ratio measures the company's ability to fulfill its financial obligations in the short term. Bank that has Current A high ratio is considered more liquid and better able to meet short-term obligations. This can affect bank PER, because investors tend to give higher value to companies that are considered more liquid and capable of meeting their financial obligations in the short term.

(4) Debt to Equity Ratio/DER. A high DPR can increase PER because investors will be more interested in banks that provide larger dividends. Conversely, a low DPR can reduce PER because investors will be more interested in banks that provide larger dividends.

(5) Dividend Payout Ratio/DPR. A high DPR can increase PER because investors will be more interested in banks that provide larger dividends. Conversely, a low DPR can reduce PER because investors will be more interested in banks that provide larger dividends.

(6) Dividend Growth. Stable and increasing dividend growth over time can increase PER because investors will consider the bank as a stable and reliable investment. On the other hand, if dividend growth is low or unstable, this can reduce PER because investors will consider the bank to be a less attractive investment.

(7) Earning growth. Stable and increasing earnings growth over time can increase PER because investors will consider the bank as an investment that has the potential to generate greater profits in the future. On the other hand, if earnings growth is low or unstable, this can reduce PER because investors will consider the bank as a less attractive investment.

(8) Earnings Per Share/EPS. High EPS can increase PER because investors will be more interested in banks that have higher net income per share. Conversely, low EPS can reduce PER because investors will consider the bank to be less profitable.

(9) Fixed Asset Turnover/FAT. High EPS can increase PER because investors will be more interested in banks that have higher net income per share. Conversely, low EPS can reduce PER because investors will consider the bank to be less profitable.

(10) Fixed Leverage Ratio/FLR. High EPS can increase PER because investors will be more interested in banks that have higher net income per share. Conversely, low EPS can reduce PER because investors will consider the bank to be less profitable.

(11) Financial Leverage. High financial leverage can increase PER because banks can use debt to obtain additional capital and increase their net profit. However, financial leverage that is too high can also pose greater risks for investors and reduce PER. Therefore, balanced financial leverage can increase PER in banking.

(12) Growth Rate of Earnings/GRO. A high GRO can increase PER because investors will think that the bank has better business prospects and can generate greater profits in the future. On the other hand, a low GRO can reduce PER because investors will think that the bank has poor business prospects and is less profitable.

(13) Good Corporate Governance/GCG. Good GCG can increase PER because investors will have more confidence in bank management and consider the bank to be more stable and reliable. On the other hand, poor GCG can

reduce PER because investors will have less confidence in bank management and consider the bank to be less stable and reliable.

(14) Share price. High share prices can increase PER because investors will assume the bank has good performance and bright business prospects. Conversely, low share prices can reduce PER because investors will consider the bank less attractive and less profitable.

(15) Inventory Turnover/INTO. High INTO can increase PER because investors will think that the bank can maximize the use of resources efficiently and effectively. On the other hand, low INTO can reduce PER because investors will consider the bank to be less efficient in managing inventory.

(16) Interest Rate. A high interest rate can increase PER because investors will think that the bank can maximize the use of resources efficiently and effectively. On the other hand, a low interest rate can reduce PER because investors will consider the bank to be less efficient in managing inventory.

(17) Number of outstanding shares. A low number of outstanding shares can increase PER because it can increase demand for these shares from investors. On the other hand, a high number of outstanding shares can reduce PER because it can reduce demand for these shares from investors.

(18) Inflation. High inflation can reduce PER because it can reduce people's purchasing power and increase bank operational costs. On the other hand, low inflation can increase PER because it can increase people's purchasing power and reduce bank operational costs.

(19) Dividend policy. A good investment opportunity can increase PER because it can show that the company has the potential to gain greater profits in the future. On the other hand, a bad investment opportunity can reduce PER because it can indicate that the company has a greater risk in gaining profits in the future.

(20) Investment opportunities. A good investment opportunity can increase PER because it can show that the company has the potential to gain greater profits in the future. On the other hand, a bad investment opportunity can reduce PER because it can indicate that the company has a greater risk in gaining profits in the future.

(21) Institutional ownership. High institutional ownership can increase PER because it can show institutional investors' confidence in the company's performance and future prospects. Conversely, low institutional ownership can reduce PER because it can indicate a lack of interest from institutional investors in the company.

(22) Net profit. High net profit can increase PER because it shows that the company is able to generate good profits. On the other hand, low net profit can reduce PER because it shows that the company is having difficulty generating profits.

(23) Loan to Deposit Ratio/LDR. A high LDR can reduce PER because it can indicate that the bank is having difficulty managing credit risk. On the other hand, a low LDR can increase PER because it shows that the bank is able to manage credit risk well.

(24) Liquidity. High liquidity can increase PER because it shows that the bank has the ability to fulfill its financial obligations in the short term. On the other hand, low liquidity can reduce PER because it shows that the bank is having difficulty meeting its financial obligations in the short term.

(25) Inventory accounting/valuation methods. The accounting/inventory valuation method used can influence the PER in banking. If the company uses the LIFO (Last-In, First-Out) method, then inventory costs will be higher, which

can reduce net profit and PER. On the other hand, if the company uses the FIFO (First-In, First-Out) method, inventory costs will be lower, which can increase net profit and PER.

(26) Net Interest Margin/NIM. NIM is a ratio that measures the difference between interest income and interest costs received by the bank. A high NIM can increase net profit and PER because it shows that the bank can generate more income from its business. Conversely, low NIM can reduce net profit and PER.

(27) Non Performing Loans/NPL. NPL is a ratio that measures the amount of loans that are not paid on time. Low NPL can increase PER because it shows that the bank has good credit quality and manages credit risk well. On the other hand, a high NPL can reduce PER because it shows that the bank is having difficulty managing credit risk.

(28) Net Profit Margin/NPM. NPM is a ratio that measures net profit as a percentage of revenue. A high NPM can increase PER because it shows that the bank can generate greater net profits from its business. Conversely, low NPM can reduce PER.

(29) Operating Profit. Operating profit can influence PER in banking because it can provide an indication of how effective the bank is in generating profits from its core operations. The higher the operating profit, the greater the possibility that the bank has the ability to earn consistent profits in the future. This can increase investor confidence and increase PER.

(30) Quick Ratio. The quick ratio can influence PER in banking because it can provide an overview of the bank's ability to fulfill its short-term obligations. The higher the quick ratio, the greater the possibility that the bank has the ability to meet its financial obligations in the short term. This can increase investor confidence and increase PER.

(31) Distribution of shares. The distribution of shares (stock split) can affect PER in banking because it can affect share prices and the number of shares outstanding. Share distribution can reduce the share price but increase the number of shares outstanding. This can increase stock liquidity and increase investor interest in the stock, which can increase PER.

(32) Earning Growth. Income growth can influence PER in banking because it can provide an indication of how quickly a bank can obtain new income from its operations. The higher the revenue growth, the greater the likelihood that the bank will be able to provide consistent profits in the future. This can increase investor confidence and increase PER.

(33) Profit growth. Profit growth can influence PER in banking because it can provide an indication of how effective the bank is in generating profits from its core operations. The higher the profit growth, the greater the possibility that the bank has the ability to earn consistent profits in the future. This can increase investor confidence and increase PER.

(34) Growth in Earnings Before Interest and Taxes/EBIT. EBIT growth can influence PER in banking because it can provide an indication of how effective the bank is in generating income from its operations without considering interest and tax factors. The higher the EBIT growth, the more likely the bank has the ability to earn consistent profits in the future. This can increase investor confidence and increase PER.

(35) Acceptance of Going Concern audit opinion. Acceptance of a Going Concern audit opinion can influence PER in banking because it can provide an indication of how good the bank's financial condition is in the long term. If Going Concern's audit opinion is accepted, this shows that the bank has the ability to

survive and operate in the long term. This can increase investor confidence and increase PER.

(36) Price Book Value/PBV. PBV (book price per share) can influence PER in banking because it can provide an indication of how much the bank's assets are worth compared to its share price. If PBV is high, this indicates that investors are paying more for each dollar of bank assets compared to the price of its shares. This can show that investors have high confidence in the bank's ability to generate profits in the future, which can increase PER.

(37) PSAK 72. Implementation of PSAK 72 can affect PER in banking because changes in the recognition and measurement of financial instruments can affect bank financial reports and their performance. If this change results in an increase in bank profits, then this can increase PER.

(38) Rate of Return. RoR can influence PER in banking because banks that have a higher RoR tend to have a higher PER. This is because investors will pay more for bank shares that can provide higher investment returns.

(39) Debt ratio. The debt ratio can affect the PER in banking because banks that have a higher debt ratio tend to have a lower PER. This is because investors will consider banks with lower debt ratios to be safer and have the ability to generate more stable profits in the future.

(40) Return On Assets/ROA. ROA can influence PER in banking because banks with higher ROA tend to have higher PER. This is because investors tend to pay more for bank shares that have the ability to generate better profits from the assets they own.

(41) Return On Equity/ROE. ROE can influence PER in banking because banks with higher ROE tend to have higher PER. This is because investors tend to pay more for bank shares that have the ability to generate better profits from the equity they own.

(42) Systematic Risk. Systematic risk can affect PER in banking because investors will consider systematic risk in choosing bank shares. If the systematic risk on the market is very high, investors tend to choose bank shares with a lower PER because they are considered more stable.

(43) Capital structure. Capital structure can influence PER in banking because banks with more stable capital structures tend to have higher PER. This is because investors tend to choose banks that have a stable capital structure and are considered to be able to provide more consistent investment results.

(44) Ownership structure. Ownership structure can influence PER in banking because investors tend to have more confidence in banks owned by large financial institutions or prominent individuals. This can affect PER because investors tend to pay more for bank shares that are considered more trustworthy.

(45) Interest rate. Interest rates can affect the PER in banking because banks with higher interest rates tend to have higher PER. This is because investors tend to pay more for bank shares that are considered to have greater income potential from high interest rates.

(46) Standard Deviation Earnings Growth. The standard deviation of profit growth can influence PER in banking because investors tend to choose banks with stable profit growth and are considered to be able to provide more consistent investment results. This can affect PER because investors tend to pay more for bank shares that are considered to have stable and reliable profit growth.

(47) Total Asset Turnover/TATO. TATO measures how efficiently a bank uses its assets to generate income. The higher the TATO, the more efficient the bank is in generating income from its assets. In this case, the higher the TATO, the higher the possibility of the bank having a high PER because the bank is able to generate greater income with the assets it owns.

(48) Company size. Company size, as measured by total assets, can influence PER in banking. Company size can provide advantages in terms of savings in scale, risk diversification, and also reliance on greater financial resources. Large companies can have the ability to handle greater market risk and volatility, which can boost investor confidence and increase PER.

(49) Earnings variability. Profit variability measures how much a bank's revenue or profit fluctuates over time. The lower the earnings variability, the more stable the bank's performance and the higher the probability of a higher PER. Conversely, the higher the variability of earnings, the greater the risk borne by investors and the lower the possibility of a higher PER.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded as follows: first, based on the mapping of the distribution of journal publications regarding the Price Earning Ratio (PER) ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking during the period 2001 to 2022 originating from the accredited national journal Sinta, there are 571 published journal articles. Second, based on VOSviewer bibliometric study mapping, the network visualization results regarding the PER ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking are divided into 4 clusters and 178 topic items. Cluster 1 consists of 79 topics, cluster 2 consists of 54 topics, cluster 3 consists of 42 topics, and cluster 4 consists of 3 topics. Third, based on mapping studies literature review, there are 31 topics related to the influence of the PER ratio on Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely: stock beta, Cumulative Abnormal Return, Debt to Equity Ratio/DER, stock prices, stock interistic prices, investment decisions, dividend policy, corporate social performance, financial performance, performance portfolio, company profit, working capital Net Asset Value/NAV, company value, income smoothing, stock prospects, stock income, income growth, dividend distribution, market performance, Price Book Value/PBV, Stock portfolio return, Return On Assets/ROA, Return On Equity/ROE, Stock market returns, systematic risk, capital structure, underpricing of initial shares, stock returns, stock valuation, and stock trading volume. And there are 49 topics related to the determinants of the PER ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely: Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR, Corporate Social Responsibility/CSR, Current Ratio, Debt to Equity Ratio/DER, Dividend Payout Ratio/DPR, Dividend Growth, Earning growth, Earning Per Share/EPS, Fixed Asset Turnover/FAT, Fixed Leverage Ratio/FLR, Financial Leverage, Growth Rate of Earning/GRO, Good Corporate Governance/GCG, share price, Inventory Turnover/INTO, Interest Rate, number of outstanding shares, inflation, dividend policy, investment opportunities, institutional ownership, net profit, Loan to Deposit Ratio/LDR, liquidity, accounting/inventory valuation methods, Net Interest Margin/NIM, Non-Performing Loans/NPL, Net Profit Margin/NPM, Operating Profit, Quick Ratio, share distribution, income growth/Earnings Growth, profit growth, Growth in Earnings Before Interest and Taxes/Ebit, Acceptance of Going Concern audit opinion, Price Book Value/PBV, PSAK 72, Rate of Return, debt ratio, Return On Assets/ROA, Return On Equity/ROE, Systematic Risk, capital

structure, ownership structure, interest rates, Standard Deviation Earning Growth, Total Asset Turnover/TATO, company size, and profit variability.

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